

Generalized numerical solution of the time-independent Schrödinger equation

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Abstract

The Schrödinger equation is the most fundamental equation in quantum mechanics. We will try to numerically solve the unidimensional time-independent Schrödinger equation for constant potentials using Numerov's method (sometimes referred to as Cowell's method). The standard approach is to find the energy eigenvalues and infer the wave functions thereon. In contrast to that, we will try to find the generalized wave functions and then infer the energy eigenvalues. We start with a constant potential in infinite space, find the general solution then particularise the wave function to a potential well.

1 Introduction

A second-order linear ordinary differential equation in can be written in the form

$$Ay_{xx} + By_x + Cy + D = 0 \tag{1}$$

Where A, B, C, D are all functions in x . Numerov's method can be used to solve ordinary differential equations when $B = 0$. It is a fourth-order linear multistep method. The method is implicit, but can be made explicit if the differential equation is linear.

The method was developed by the Russian astronomer, Boris Vasilyevich Numerov (1891-1941). The lunar crater Numerov and the minor planet 1206 Numerowia, discovered by the German astronomer Karl Reinmuth in Heidelberg in 1931, were named in his honour[1]. This honour would later have serious consequences on his life.

In October 1936, during the Second World War, he was arrested and then sentenced to 10 years hard labour after being accused of being a German spy. This accusation rested on the fact that German astronomers had named a lunar crater after him. It was assumed that he was executed along with other political prisoners in September 1941 at the Oryol Prison, Russia before the city's surrender to the Nazi army.

2 Numerov's method

When $B = 0$, Eqn(1) can be rearranged in the form

$$y_{xx} = -\frac{C}{A}y - \frac{D}{A} \quad (2)$$

After substituting $g(x) = \frac{C(x)}{A(x)}$ and $s(x) = -\frac{D(x)}{A(x)}$, we get[2]

$$y''(x) = -g(x)y(x) + s(x) \quad (3)$$

The Numerov's method for solving this equation, can be derived by an elementary application of Taylor expansion. We begin with the Taylor expansion of the function we want to solve, $y(x)$, around the point x_0

$$y(x) = y(x_0) + (x-x_0)y'(x_0) + \frac{(x-x_0)^2}{2!}y''(x_0) + \dots + \frac{(x-x_0)^5}{5!}y^{(5)}(x_0) + \mathcal{O}(h^6) \quad (4)$$

Denoting the distance from x to x_0 by $h = x - x_0$, we can write the above equation as

$$y(x_0+h) = y(x_0) + hy'(x_0) + \frac{h^2}{2!}y''(x_0) + \frac{h^3}{3!}y'''(x_0) + \frac{h^4}{4!}y^{(4)}(x_0) + \frac{h^5}{5!}y^{(5)}(x_0) + \mathcal{O}(h^6) \quad (5)$$

If we evenly discretize the space, we get a number line of x points, where $h = x_{n+1} - x_n$. By applying the above equations to this discrete space, we get a relation between the y_n and y_{n+1}

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + hy'(x_n) + \frac{h^2}{2!}y''(x_n) + \frac{h^3}{3!}y'''(x_n) + \frac{h^4}{4!}y^{(4)}(x_n) + \frac{h^5}{5!}y^{(5)}(x_n) + \mathcal{O}(h^6) \quad (6)$$

Computationally, this amounts to taking a step "forward" by an amount h . If we want to take a step "backwards", we replace every h with $-h$ and get the expression for y_{n-1}

$$y_{n-1} = y_n - hy'(x_n) + \frac{h^2}{2!}y''(x_n) - \frac{h^3}{3!}y'''(x_n) + \frac{h^4}{4!}y^{(4)}(x_n) - \frac{h^5}{5!}y^{(5)}(x_n) + \mathcal{O}(h^6) \quad (7)$$

By summing the two equations, we derive that

$$y_{n+1} - 2y_n + y_{n-1} = h^2y''_n + \frac{h^4}{12}y^{(4)}_n + \mathcal{O}(h^6) \quad (8)$$

We can solve this equation for y_{n+1} by substituting the expression given at the beginning, that is $y''_n = -g_n y_n + s_n$. To get an expression for the $y^{(4)}_n$ factor, we simply have to differentiate $y''_n = -g_n y_n + s_n$ twice and approximate it again in the same way we did this above

$$y^{(4)}_n = \frac{d^2}{dx^2}(-g_n y_n + s_n), \quad (9)$$

$$h^2 y_n'''' = -g_{n+1} y_{n+1} + s_{n+1} + 2g_n y_n - 2s_n - g_{n-1} y_{n-1} + s_{n-1} + \mathcal{O}(h^4). \quad (10)$$

If we now substitute this to the preceding equation, we get

$$y_{n+1} \left(1 + \frac{h^2}{12} g_{n+1}\right) - 2y_n \left(1 - \frac{5h^2}{12} g_n\right) + y_{n-1} \left(1 + \frac{h^2}{12} g_{n-1}\right) = \frac{h^2}{12} (s_{n+1} + 10s_n + s_{n-1}) + \mathcal{O}(h^6). \quad (11)$$

This yields the numerical Numerov's method iteration relation.

3 Schrödinger equation

The unidimensional time-independent Schrödinger equation can be written as

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2 \psi}{dx^2} + V(x) \psi(x) = E \psi(x) \quad (12)$$

Where $\psi(x)$ is the wave function, $V(x)$ is the potential, m is the mass of the particle and E is the energy of the system.

Rewriting,

$$\frac{d^2 \psi}{dx^2} = -\frac{2m}{\hbar^2} (E - V(x)) \psi(x) \quad (13)$$

This is analogous to Eqn(3) with

$$g(x) = \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} (E - V(x)) \quad (14)$$

And,

$$s(x) = 0 \quad (15)$$

4 Numerical solution of Schrödinger equation

For our problem we consider a constant potential V_0 in the space $x \in [0, \infty)$ and impose the initial conditions of $\psi(0) = 0$, $\psi'(0) = 1$. The solution can be later extended for the space $x \in (-\infty, 0)$ using the iteration relation obtained.

After substituting $V' = \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} (E - V_0)$, eqn(13) becomes,

$$\frac{d^2 \psi}{dx^2} + V' \psi = 0 \quad (16)$$

And eqn(14) becomes,

$$g(x) = V' \quad (17)$$

To solve the problem using Numerov's method, we discretize this problem with $h = 1$. Since V' is a constant,

$$g_n = g_{n+1} = g_{n-1} = V' \quad (18)$$

We have $\psi_0 = 0$, and

$$\psi'_0 = \frac{\psi_1 - \psi_0}{h} = \frac{\psi_1 - 0}{1} = 1 \quad (19)$$

Thus, $\psi_1 = 1$.

Using eqn(11) and neglecting the higher order terms, we derive that

$$\psi_{n+1} \left(1 + \frac{V'}{12}\right) + \psi_{n-1} \left(1 + \frac{V'}{12}\right) = 2\psi_n \left(1 - \frac{5V'}{12}\right) \quad (20)$$

$$\left(\frac{\psi_{n+1} + \psi_{n-1}}{2}\right) \left(\frac{V' + 12}{12 - 5V'}\right) = \psi_n \quad (21)$$

After substituting $A = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{V'+12}{12-5V'}\right)$,

$$\psi_{n+1} + \psi_{n-1} = \frac{\psi_n}{A} \quad (22)$$

$$\psi_{n+1} = \frac{\psi_n}{A} - \psi_{n-1} \quad (23)$$

For the n -th index,

$$\psi_n = \frac{\psi_{n-1}}{A} - \psi_{n-2} \quad (24)$$

We know the values of ψ_0, ψ_1 and can use them to construct a series solution using the above iteration relation.

5 Matlab solution

The iteration relation in eqn(24) can be used to obtain ψ at different values of x that can be used to obtain a plot of ψ vs x . This has been done in Fig. 1 using Matlab[3] for $V' = 0.1$ and $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 100$.

5.1 Matlab code

```
v=0.1;
a=0.5*(12+v)/(12-5*v);
y=0;
y(1)=0;
y(2)=1;
for i=3:100
y(i)=y(i-1)/a-y(i-2);
end
x=[1:100];
plot(x,y);
xlabel("x\rightarrow","FontSize",20);
ylabel(" u(x)\rightarrow","FontSize",20);
```


Figure 1: Plot of ψ vs x with $V' = 0.1$ and $x = [1, 100]$

6 Analytical solution

Let us compare the numerical solution to the untampered analytical solution. For our problem the Schrödinger equation becomes,

$$\frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} + V'\psi = 0 \quad (25)$$

The general solution to this equation is of form

$$\psi(x) = C_1 \sin(\sqrt{V'}x) + C_2 \cos(\sqrt{V'}x) \quad (26)$$

When we impose the initial conditions of $\psi(0) = 0$, $\psi'(0) = 1$; we get the values $C_2 = 0$ and $C_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{V'}}$.

Therefore,

$$\psi(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{V'}} \sin(\sqrt{V'}x) \quad (27)$$

For $V' = 0.1$, the amplitude becomes 3.16 and the frequency becomes 0.32. This is what we have obtained numerically in the plot in Fig. 1.

Thus, the numerical solution that we obtained from Numerov's method is pretty close to the analytical solution. A similar approach can be used to solve the angular form of Schrödinger equation for a spherically symmetric potential (as is the case in the Hydrogen atom).

7 Potential well

We consider the special case of the infinite square well which is given by the condition

$$V(x) = \begin{cases} V_0 & 0 \leq x < L \\ \infty & x \geq L \end{cases}$$

The analytical solution in this case is given by

$$\psi_k(x) = \frac{L}{k\pi} \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{L}x\right) \quad (28)$$

Where $k = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

In this case the values for V' cannot be arbitrary, rather they are specified according to the equation

$$V'_k = \frac{k^2\pi^2}{L^2} \quad (29)$$

The energy eigen values are

$$E_k = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} V'_k + V_0 \quad (30)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_k = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{V'_k}{V_0} + 1 \quad (31)$$

Where $\mathcal{E}_k = \frac{E_k}{V_0}$ is the non-dimensional energy eigen value. We take $mV_0 = \frac{\hbar^2}{2}$. Therefore,

$$\mathcal{E}_k = V'_k + 1 \quad (32)$$

Different energy eigen values thus calculated are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Non-dimensional energy eigen values for $L = 10$

k	V'_k	\mathcal{E}_k
1	0.099	1.099
2	0.395	1.395
3	0.888	1.888
4	1.579	2.579
5	2.467	3.467

References

- [1] (1206) *Numerowia*, pp. 101–101. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2007.
- [2] E. Hairer, S. Norsett, and G. Wanner, *Solving Ordinary Differential Equations I: Nonstiff Problems*, vol. 8. 01 1993.
- [3] MATLAB, *version 7.10.0 (R2010a)*. Natick, Massachusetts: The MathWorks Inc., 2010.